

DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF TEACHING THE QUANTUM PHYSICS DEPARTMENT IN ACADEMIC LYCEUMS

Y.Sh. Dusov

Teacher of physics, Department of Exact and Natural Sciences, Military Academic Lyceum
"Young Border

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Abstract. *In this article, digital technologies do not just turn the learning process into a presentation tool, but also turn the student into an active subject. For example, using animated models to explain topics such as the movement of molecules, the increase in speed of electrons leaving the surface of a metal, and the formation of photocurrents, “revive” the laws of physics before the eyes of the student. This situation serves to form a visual perception of abstract concepts in the student. The integration of digital technologies in the modern educational process has become not only a requirement of the time, but also one of the main factors in increasing the effectiveness of education. The richness of complex, abstract concepts in the science of physics requires the introduction of visualization and interactive approaches in teaching this subject. In this regard, a number of digital platforms and tools are being used both around the world and in the education system of Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *digital, technologies, tools, animation, models, electronics, laws of physics, abstraction, integration, digital platform.*

INTRODUCTION. It has been demonstrated that nowadays the widespread penetration of digital technologies into the education system necessitates the development of digital media competence in students' professional training. This competence encompasses not only the ability to search for and analyze information, but also its critical evaluation, processing, and effective presentation. In particular, the effective use of existing didactic capabilities is crucial in this process. Modern didactic capabilities, such as digital tools, interactive platforms, online educational resources, and multimedia materials, make the learning process more effective, engaging, and personalized. In this regard, the role of didactic approaches in developing digital media competence is invaluable, as they serve as a key factor in increasing student engagement and fostering independent thinking.

For several centuries, the exact and natural sciences have flourished in Uzbekistan, and the Central Asian region has become the intellectual center of the world. The First and Second Renaissance eras, which originated in our country, gave birth to outstanding geniuses recognized worldwide. Today, there is an urgent need to improve the quality of physics teaching in secondary schools, integrate modern teaching methods into the educational process, select talented students, train competitive specialists for the labor market, and develop scientific research and innovation, focusing on practical effectiveness. See the "Overview" section.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-5032 dated March 19, 2021, ushered in a new era in the development of physics.

Academic lyceums are a preparatory stage for higher education and function as specialized educational institutions aimed at developing students' interest in scientific research, critical

thinking, and practical skills. Therefore, physics, particularly the Department of Quantum Physics, occupies a central place in education at the lyceum level. This department develops students' scientific thinking based on an understanding of microscopic phenomena, modeling thermal processes, and an understanding of fundamental laws such as the energy cycle and conservation of energy.

It should be emphasized that innovativeness is one of the key characteristics of modern education. The development and implementation of any innovation (new method, tool, technology) can be considered an innovation in pedagogical education. According to the Strategy for Innovative Development of Our Country until 2030, the foundation of all innovative changes is the provision of software in specialized areas. The purpose of software is to create conditions for developing the competencies of innovative individuals in citizens who, as innovative individuals, are ready and able to adapt to all changes in society.

The topic is Innovative individuals shape an innovative society and are distinguished by the skills of continuous learning, self-development, independent study, and independent work. The stages of development of modern education are characterized by the emergence of new theories and practices, fully covered by software. This process is associated with the development and implementation of innovative innovations based on non-traditional methods in the education system in the context of socio-economic development in all sectors of the national economy. After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, positive changes began in education, along with all other spheres.

Discussions. It is well established that for our independent Republic to find its place in the global community, attract foreign investment, transition to a market economy, and keep pace with scientific and technological development, it is essential to train competent personnel who meet international standards. Leading countries such as the United Kingdom, Canada, the United States, South Korea, and Russia are systematically developing pedagogical processes based on the use of innovative technologies in education. Projects are being implemented on the theme of "Formation of a 'teacher-student-educational tool' educational environment," developing students' creative thinking, utilizing modern educational technologies, and meeting the need for software based on the development of students' information culture. The development of society relies on information and knowledge. Today, the rapid spread of various forms of media and information and communication technologies and their impact on our personal, economic, political, and social lives is undeniable. Information plays a central role in people's lives, and effective participation in it requires new knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The frequently used term "literacy" is now used interchangeably with terms such as "digital," "computer," "visual," "technological," "communication," and, of course, "media" and "information." This tradition reflects the growing interest in research in this area and the rapid changes in modern society.

In particular, priority projects are being implemented to improve the e-government system, further develop the local software and information technology market, establish IT centers in all regions of the republic, and provide the industry with qualified personnel. It is evident that the needs of the state and society are changing the goals and content of developing students' information literacy. Despite the theoretical development of issues related to developing students' information literacy using various approaches, the pace of globalization, the transition to a unified governance system—that is, an information society—and new trends in science and education reinforce the need to develop modern requirements for developing students' information literacy.

Figure 1. The Need to Develop an Information Culture

There is convincing evidence to suggest that increasing the effectiveness of knowledge acquired by students in academic lyceums is one of the factors stimulating the development of the state. A commitment to mastering educational content leads to a creative approach and independent knowledge acquisition. The need for progressively thinking teachers who meet the demands of the times has always been high in society. Teachers' work is being modernized through the introduction of creative developments, scientific achievements, and advanced pedagogical practices. Knowledge is developed through scientific research methods—observation, experimentation, modeling, analogies, analysis, and synthesis. Through this, students not only acquire existing knowledge but also develop skills for independent scientific research.

Table 1.

Modern Technologies Used in Physics Teaching in Academic Lyceums

Technological tool	Description	Impact on students
PhET Simulations	Demonstrates physical laws through visual experiments	Facilitates understanding, increases interest in experimentation
Mobile apps (PhyWiz, Pocket Physics)	Independent study tool, problems, theoretical materials	Allows for independent learning, repetition, and error correction
Gamification elements	Incentives through points, rankings, and competitions	Actively engages in the lesson, increases motivation
Virtual Labs (Online)	Laboratory simulation tool	Gives every student an experimental experience
STEAM approach	Connects physics, technology, and engineering	Develops practical, creative and systematic thinking

It is generally acknowledged within the field that results from physics teachers using the STEAM approach demonstrate that conducting physics experiments using microcontrollers such

as Arduino and Raspberry Pi engages students in solving real-world problems. This, in turn, transforms physics from a "dry theory" into a meaningful, practical field.

Gamification is based on organizing lessons using game elements. For example, activities such as online tests like the "Physics Quiz," "Top 5 Students" rankings, and the "Science Marathon" enhance competitiveness and encourage students to work independently. The integration of digital technologies into the modern educational process has become not only a requirement of the times but also a key factor in improving learning effectiveness. The wealth of complex, abstract concepts in physics requires the introduction of visualization and interactive approaches to teaching this subject. Therefore, a number of digital platforms and tools are used both internationally and in the education system of Uzbekistan.

Analysis of international platforms. PhET Interactive Simulations (USA): PhET is a set of interactive simulations created by the University of Colorado. Photoelectric effect. Theory and laws of the photoelectric effect. Einstein's equation. Light pressure. Lebedev's experiment. Chemical effects of light. More than 100 simulations. Advantages: free, clear, available in many languages; disadvantages: lack of Uzbek language, weak connection with lab assignments [15].

Yenka/Crocodile Physics (UK): a software tool designed for modeling many areas of physics, especially quantum physics processes. It has a powerful graphical interface. Its disadvantages include its high cost and the need for powerful computing hardware [16].

Khan Academy (USA): A collection of video lessons, exercises, and tests on physics. Topics include molecular motion, energy, and heat. Advantages: free and interactive; disadvantages: not available in Uzbek and no practical module [17].

Uzbekistan experience. Ziyonet (Republic of Uzbekistan): An educational resources portal that includes educational and methodological materials, tests, and video lessons in various subjects. There is content on physics. The disadvantage is that there are no simulations or virtual laboratories [18].

Maktab.uz: Online lessons portal. There are video lessons in all subjects, including physics. However, these lessons are based on a theoretical approach, and there is no interactivity or laboratory work [20].

1.2.2 Analytical table

Online lessons portal. Advantages Disadvantages

The name of platform	Organization / Country	Advantages	Disadvantages
PhET	USA (Colorado Univ.)	Interactive simulation, free, multilingual	No Uzbek, weak assignment module
Yenka / Crocodile	Great Britain	Powerful graphical interface, complex process modeling	Requires expensive, powerful equipment
Khan Academy	USA	Video lessons, tests, independent study opportunities	No Uzbek language, no laboratory work available
ZiyoNET	Uzbekistan	Multilingual resources, tests, lesson materials	No interactivity, no lab
Maktab.uz	Uzbekistan	Lesson videos available	Theoretically, no laboratory available

It has become increasingly apparent that innovative electronic didactic forms of learning represent a system of interaction between teacher and student, based on psychological, general pedagogical, didactic, and personal-methodological approaches aimed at designing educational content in accordance with the educational goal, taking into account the student's abilities and interests, as well as implementing pedagogical, information and communication methods, forms, and methods of teaching.

In general, according to Light, Greg, and Cox Roy, educational content should meet the following requirements:

- be a means of developing students' cognitive abilities;
- be the basis for shaping students' experience;
- develop students' critical thinking, reflective abilities, independence, and creativity;
- meet students' educational needs and simultaneously develop them.

Systematic physics learning should be understood as the creation of specific interconnections in the study of individual sections and, as a result, the expansion of knowledge and skills acquired at individual stages of physics learning. A systematic educational process at all

levels of education requires the development and use of unified and unique methods for studying physics, enhancing the role of student independent work.

Physics education research (PER) is a form of research in the area of disciplinary transfer related to the teaching and learning of physics, conducted with the goal of improving the effectiveness of student learning and developing them into competent specialists in this field. This area of pedagogical science is studied by a huge number of educational institutions worldwide, including at least 85 higher education institutions in the United States alone dedicated to the development of natural science and physical education. One expert successfully working in this field, Robert Beichner, in his work "Introduction to Research in Physics Education," identified seven areas of research in physics education.

It is widely recognized in academic circles that the principle of systematicity and the correspondence between the components of the educational process ensures the continuity of education and the connection between educational institutions. Interconnection in the educational system is achieved by integrating educational information at different levels of education. However, the current modernization of educational content, based on various aspects (e.g., organizational and structural), and the creation of various alternative programs give rise to numerous problems. Applying the principle of systems approach to the study of various branches of science, such as physics, requires in-depth research. In this situation, it is appropriate to identify the acquisition of high-quality knowledge with a comprehensive understanding of physics as the primary goals. However, in the question of "science and subject matter," which is rarely mentioned by most researchers, the distinction between scientific and academic knowledge is clearly evident. From this perspective, the current curricula of higher education institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan are difficult to combine in terms of scope, content, and interrelationships.

The systematic nature of physics learning should be understood as the interconnectedness of its various branches. Consequently, the development of abilities occurs as knowledge expands at different stages of the subject's study. Therefore, one of the primary goals of research in the teaching of various branches of the physical sciences is to develop pedagogical methods and strategies that will help students effectively master physics, as well as assist teachers in using these methods and strategies. Therefore, research in physics teaching typically aims to identify the most common errors and misconceptions. The primary research effort currently required is to address the challenges of providing detailed knowledge of physics in lectures, practical classes, and workshops, as well as other types of educational process, which are the most common methods in physics education. This situation is linked to the process of knowledge transfer and, therefore, poses challenges for teachers, students, and learners involved in this process, as well as the content of the training, the teaching materials used in the curricula, and the resources of educational institutions. These challenges require successful resolution. Didactic support includes lecture texts, slide presentation sets, handouts, visual aids, object models, audio or video demonstrations, exercise sets, problem sets, test sets, and assignment sets. The purpose of didactic support is to effectively organize classes, increase student interest in science, and develop a sense of why science should be studied. The objectives of didactic support are:

- description and explanation of educational processes and the conditions for their implementation;
- improved organization of the educational process, i.e., the development of educational systems and technologies;

- identification of general patterns characteristic of the educational process, analysis of their factors, and description.

Figure 2. Didactic Foundations of Modern Approaches in Education

It cannot be claimed that these skills and abilities are sufficient for all teachers. Electronic didactic support for the development of professional skills represents a system of resources, tools, and methods that support the educational process and are aimed at improving it. The above analysis shows that the current system of teaching quantum physics in academic lyceums faces a number of problems. **These problems manifest** themselves in the following key areas:

1. Insufficient digital teaching tools: Currently used digital platforms (e.g., PhET, Khan Academy, Ziyonet, Edu.uz) are not fully and seamlessly integrated, and the lack of practical laboratory work and virtual experiments hinders in-depth mastery of these subjects. Low interest in natural science: According to statistics, in recent years, student interest in physics has remained lower than in other natural sciences. According to a 2023 report by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, physics test scores in academic lyceums were 15–20% lower than in other subjects.

2. Incompatibility of curricula with modern technologies: Most textbooks and teaching materials are far from interactive and do not meet the educational needs of the modern digital generation.

3. Lack of tools to help students learn independently: The existing system has limited capabilities for assignment banks, automated assessment tools, and performance monitoring.

Table 1. Problems in Physics Teaching and Their Negative Impact

Problem	Negative impact
Insufficient digital platforms	Practical skills are not developed, topics are not understood
Low student interest	Achievements in science decline, not chosen as elective subject
Lack of technological approach	Classes are held in a traditional format and do not meet modern requirements.
Lack of independent learning tools	Students become passive, their learning level is low

Table 2: Solutions to Problems in Teaching Physics

Problem solutions	Positive reinforcement
Analysis Choosing digital platforms	Choosing Digital Platforms in Teaching Physics
Developing a new software tool	Using new software tools
Creating methodological guides	Creating textbooks, practical, laboratory, electronic textbooks and manuals

It is important to solve the above problems, it is advisable to implement the following measures:

- Create an integrated digital platform specifically designed for academic lyceums, covering the subject of quantum physics;
- Develop multifunctional software in the Uzbek language, including visual simulations, virtual laboratories, a question bank and test modules;
- Prepare methodological guides and educational and methodological packages for teachers and students;
- Use modern technologies (AI, AR, VR) to convey science in a visual, experience-based way.

These solutions increase students' interest in science, form practical skills, and facilitate understanding of physics.

Conclusion. In the modern education system, innovative pedagogical technologies, in particular, teaching based on the STEAM approach (Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, Mathematics), play an important role in increasing the effectiveness of education. This approach to teaching exact sciences such as physics develops not only the student's level of knowledge, but also his or her creative thinking, problem-solving and practical application skills.

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